

Acropolis of Monte Polizzo

also known as "Sanctuary of Monte Polizzo"

By Kate Minniti, University of British Columbia

Entry tags: Sacred mountain, Temple, Sacred Enclosure, Ancient Mediterranean, Religious Group, Ritual centre, Elymian Religion, Sicily, Religious Place, Religious Complex

The Iron Age settlement of Monte Polizzo (713 m asl) sits upon an interconnected group of ridges in western Sicily. The settlement was plausibly founded by Elymian people at the end of the eighth century BCE and reached its peak of population after a century and a half when it underwent a massive reorganization with the creation of terraces and the building of new structures. The site is approximately 11.8 ha in size, and consists of a ceremonial acropolis surrounded by clusters of houses and other structures. The acropolis housed sacred buildings: a large circular temple (turned into a rectangular one roughly twenty-five years after its construction) dedicated to a local goddess, and other smaller sacella.

Date Range: 800 BCE - 500 BCE

Region: Monte Polizzo Acropolis

Region tags: Sicily, Italy, Western Sicily

The area of the ancient acropolis of Monte Polizzo (today Monte Polizo).

Status of Participants:

- Elite
- Religious Specialists
- Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Mühlenbock, C. (2008) Fragments from a mountain society: tradition, innovation and interaction at Archaic Monte Polizzo, Sicily. *Gotarc Series B*, 50. Göteborg.
- Source 2: Morris, I. and Tusa, S. (2004) "Scavi sull'acropoli di Monte Polizzo, 2000-2003." *Sicilia-Archeologica* 37: 35-84.
- Source 3: Mühlenbock, C. (2015) "Expanding the circle of trust: tradition and change in Iron Age communities in western Sicily." In J. Fejfer, M. Moltesen, and A. Rathje, eds., *Acta Hyberorea* 14: 239-69.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&ved=2ahUKEwjBisnk-YCEAxXiYkEHZY0AsoQFnoECA8QAQ&url=https%3A%2F%2Fcommons.und.edu%2Fcgi%2Fviewcontent.cgi%3Ffilename%3D1%26article%3books%26type%3Dadditional&usg=AOvVaw0LirnePDmqxkONBpq9EeIf&opi=89978449>
- Source 1 Description: Stanford Excavations at Monte Polizzo, Sicily. Project handbook 4th edition, 2004.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

— Yes

↳ Type of excavation:
— Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:
— Year range: 1970; 1998; 1998-2001; 1999-2000; 1999-2007; 2002-2006

Notes: 1970: Vincenzo Tusa 1998: Sebastiano Tusa and Kristian Kristiansen (University of Göteborg) 1998-2001: Christopher Prescott (University of Oslo) 1999-2000: Sebastiano Tusa 1999-2007: Ian Morris (Stanford University) 2002-2006: Christian Mühlenbock and Kristian Kristiansen

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Stanford University Excavations on the Acropolis of Monte Polizzo, Sicily

– Official or descriptive name: Sicilian-Scandinavian Archaeological Project

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation
– Mountain

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature
– Leveling of ground
– Terracing

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:
– Yes

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
– Yes

Notes: The sanctuary is on top of the acropolis, the highest point of the mountain, but is also part of the settlement.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure
– No

↳ A group of structures:
– Yes

Notes: The Archaic phase of the sacred area on the Acropolis comprises two larger structures, A5 and A1, an altar, A2, and possibly some more smaller altars.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– No

Notes: The sacred area was modified twice in the span of 50 years. Building A5, a quadrangular structure built at the beginning of the 6th century, was dismantled

around 550 BCE and replaced by Building A1, a circular hut-shrine, which was then dismantled and turned into a rectangular building by 525 BCE.

Reference: Spatafora, Francesca. "Culti E Ceramiche Greche Nei Santuari Dei Centri Indigeni Della Sicilia Occidentale". In *Ceramica Attica Da Santuari Della Grecia, Della Ionia E Dell'italia, Atti Convegno Internazionale (perugia 14-17 Marzo 2007)*, 739-57. Bari, 2009.

Reference: Morris, Ian, and Sebastiano Tusa. "Religione E Mutamento Sociale in Sicilia Occidentale, 600-400 A.c. : Scavi Sull'acropoli Di Monte Polizzo (TP), 2000-2003". *Sicilia Archeologica* 37, no. 102 (2004): 35-90.

Reference: Mühlenbock, C.. "Expanding the Circle of Trust: Tradition and Change in Iron Age Communities in Western Sicily". In *Tradition: Transmission of Culture in the Ancient World (= Danish Studies in Classical Archaeology, Acta Hyperborea 14)*, 239-68. Copenhagen, 2015.

Reference: Tusa, Sebastiano. "Da Mokarta a Monte Polizzo: La Transizione Dall'età Del Bronzo Finale All'età Del Ferro". In *Eis Acra : Insediamenti D'altura in Sicilia Dalla Preistoria Al III Sec. A.c., 27-52*. S. Sciascia, 2009.

↳ A group of features:

— No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

— Yes

Notes: The Acropolis *is* the seat of the sanctuary of the city on Monte Polizzo.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

— Worship

Reference: Mühlenbock, C.. "Expanding the Circle of Trust: Tradition and Change in Iron Age Communities in Western Sicily". In *Tradition: Transmission of Culture in the Ancient World (= Danish Studies in Classical Archaeology, Acta Hyperborea 14)*, 239-68. Copenhagen, 2015.

Reference: Öhlinger, Birgit. "Indigenous Cult Places of Local and Interregional Scale in Archaic Sicily: A Sociological Approach to Religion". Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2015.

Reference: Mühlenbock, Christian. *Fragments from a Mountain Society. Tradition, Innovation and Interaction at Archaic Monte Polizzo, Sicily.. GOTARC. Series B, Gothenburg Archaeological Theses. Göteborgs universitet*, 2008.

Reference: Morris, Ian, and Sebastiano Tusa. "Religione E Mutamento Sociale in Sicilia Occidentale, 600-400 A.c. : Scavi Sull'acropoli Di Monte Polizzo (TP), 2000-2003". *Sicilia Archeologica* 37, no. 102 (2004): 35-90.

Reference: Spatafora, Francesca. "Culti E Ceramiche Greche Nei Santuari Dei Centri Indigeni Della Sicilia Occidentale". In *Ceramica Attica Da Santuari Della Grecia, Della Ionia E Dell'italia, Atti Convegno Internazionale (perugia 14-17 Marzo 2007)*, 739-57. Bari, 2009.

Reference: Tusa, Sebastiano. "Da Mokarta a Monte Polizzo: La Transizione Dall'età Del Bronzo Finale All'età Del Ferro". In *Eis Acra : Insediamenti D'altura in Sicilia Dalla Preistoria Al III Sec. A.c., 27-52*. S. Sciascia, 2009.

↳ Worship:

— Other [specify]: The sanctuary seems to have been an important place for the worship of the local deity to whom red deer were sacrificed in large numbers. It also plausibly had a social, cultural, and political meaning as an important cultic center for the local indigenous people who purposefully refused to use the architectural shapes of Greek temples but chose instead to rebuild building A1 as a hut-shrine following their (alleged) ancestral traditions.

— Sacrificial

— Social

— Political

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

— Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: Building A5 was dismantled around 550 BCE and replaced with Building A1. Building A1 was also dismantled and rebuilt in a different shape around 525 BCE.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– For political reasons

Notes: The change in shape from quadrangular to round suggests that the inhabitants of Monte Polizzo actively chose to build a new sacred building whose shape recalled the local traditional hut-shrines to establish a direct connection with their ancestral predecessors, plausibly as a direct reaction to the aggressive expansionism of the neighbouring Greek poleis. The later dismantling of this newly-built hut-shrine and its transformation into a rectilinear building might then signify the assimilation of or surrender to foreign influences.

Reference: Spatafora, Francesca. "Culti E Ceramiche Greche Nei Santuari Dei Centri Indigeni Della Sicilia Occidentale". In *Ceramica Attica Da Santuari Della Grecia, Della Ionia E Dell'italia*, Atti Convegno Internazionale (perugia 14-17 Marzo 2007), 739-57. Bari, 2009.

Reference: Tusa, Sebastiano. "Da Mokarta a Monte Polizzo: La Transizione Dall'età Del Bronzo Finale All'età Del Ferro". In *Eis Acra : Insegiamenti D'altura in Sicilia Dalla Preistoria Al III Sec. A.c.*, 27-52. S. Sciascia, 2009.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

Notes: After the site was abandoned, the sacred buildings fell into disrepair.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The sanctuary seems to have been dedicated to a local deity associated with the hunt. The gender of this deity is currently unknown.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

— Yes

↳ Specify

— Other [specify]: It is plausible that the construction of the sanctuary on the acropolis was a community effort mandated by the city itself, but scholars do not know what its political organization looked like.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

— Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

— Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

— Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

— Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

— Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

— Other [specify]: There are no sources explaining the precise reasons behind the construction of the sanctuary.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

— Field doesn't know

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

— Yes

Reference: Mühlenbock, Christian. Fragments from a Mountain Society. Tradition, Innovation and Interaction at Archaic Monte Polizzo, Sicily.. GOTARC. Series B, Gothenburg Archaeological Theses. Göteborgs universitet, 2008.

Reference: Mühlenbock, C.. "Expanding the Circle of Trust: Tradition and Change in Iron Age Communities in Western Sicily". In Tradition: Transmission of Culture in the Ancient World (= Danish Studies in Classical Archaeology, Acta Hyperborea 14), 239-68. Copenhagen, 2015.

Reference: Morris, Ian, and Sebastiano Tusa. "Religione E Mutamento Sociale in Sicilia Occidentale, 600-400 A.c. : Scavi Sull'acropoli Di Monte Polizzo (TP), 2000-2003". Sicilia Archeologica 37, no. 102 (2004): 35-90.

Reference: Morris, Ian, Trinity Jackman, Brien Garnand, Emma Blake, Sebastiano Tusa, Pasquale Agozzino, Tara Hnatiuk, et al.. "Stanford University Excavations on the Acropolis of Monte Polizzo, Sicily, IV: Preliminary Report on the 2003 Season" 49 (2004). <https://doi.org/10.2307/4238823>.

Reference: Tusa, Sebastiano. "Da Mokarta a Monte Polizzo: La Transizione Dall'età Del Bronzo Finale All'età Del Ferro". In Eis Acra : Insediamenti D'altura in Sicilia Dalla Preistoria Al III Sec. A.c., 27-52. S. Sciascia, 2009.

Reference: Öhlinger, Birgit. "Indigenous Cult Places of Local and Interregional Scale in Archaic Sicily: A Sociological Approach to Religion". Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2015.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

— Yes

Notes: All the religious structures on the acropolis are purposefully situated on the highest point of the mountain.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

— No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

— Yes

Notes: Building A1, a circular hut-shrine then transformed into a rectilinear building, seems to have been the center of the local cult after it replaced an earlier sacred building, A5. It has an altar (A2), and is situated next to a single-slab pavement (A1e) and one (possibly two) stelae decorated with deer antlers. The area around building and its altar was also filled with traces of ritual butchering and burning of sacrificial offerings.

Reference: Morris, Ian, and Sebastiano Tusa. "Religione E Mutamento Sociale in Sicilia Occidentale, 600-400 A.c. : Scavi Sull'acropoli Di Monte Polizzo (TP), 2000-2003". *Sicilia Archeologica* 37, no. 102 (2004): 35-90.

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Reference: Spatafora, Francesca. "Culti E Ceramiche Greche Nei Santuari Dei Centri Indigeni Della Sicilia Occidentale". In *Ceramica Attica Da Santuari Della Grecia, Della Ionia E Dell'italia, Atti Convegno Internazionale (perugia 14-17 Marzo 2007)*, 739-57. Bari, 2009.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

— No

Notes: All the buildings are of modest dimensions.

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Reference: Morris, Ian, and Sebastiano Tusa. "Religione E Mutamento Sociale in Sicilia Occidentale, 600-400 A.c. : Scavi Sull'acropoli Di Monte Polizzo (TP), 2000-2003". *Sicilia Archeologica* 37, no. 102 (2004): 35-90.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

— Yes

Reference: Mühlenbock, Christian. *Fragments from a Mountain Society. Tradition, Innovation and Interaction at Archaic Monte Polizzo, Sicily.*. GOTARC. Series B, Gothenburg Archaeological Theses. Göteborgs universitet, 2008.

Reference: Mühlenbock, C.. "Expanding the Circle of Trust: Tradition and Change in Iron Age Communities in Western Sicily". In *Tradition: Transmission of Culture in the Ancient World (= Danish Studies in Classical Archaeology, Acta Hyperborea 14)*, 239-68. Copenhagen, 2015.

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↳ Earth

— Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

— Yes

- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Sand
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Clay
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Plaster
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Wood
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Grass
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Stone
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: There would have been metal elements in the various structures (e.g. nails, hinges, hooks), and it is possible that they may have been made of alloys such as bronze.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most buildings have not been preserved to a degree that it is possible to ascertain whether they were decorated. However, it is highly likely that they had at least some form of decoration (possibly

embedded in the architecture).

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As no decoration has survived, it is not possible to answer this question. It is not implausible, but simply impossible to prove.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The dedicatee of the sanctuary was a deity plausibly connected with the hunt, to whom thousands of red deer skulls and antlers were dedicated. The gender of this deity is currently unknown.

Reference: Mühlenbock, C. "Expanding the Circle of Trust: Tradition and Change in Iron Age Communities in Western Sicily". In *Tradition: Transmission of Culture in the Ancient World* (= Danish Studies in Classical Archaeology, Acta Hyperborea 14), 239–68. Copenhagen, 2015.

Reference: Öhlinger, Birgit. "Indigenous Cult Places of Local and Interregional Scale in Archaic Sicily: A Sociological Approach to Religion". Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2015.

Reference: Larson, Jennifer. "Venison for Artemis? the Problem of Deer Sacrifice". Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781139017886.003>.

Reference: Morris, Ian, and Sebastiano Tusa. "Religione E Mutamento Sociale in Sicilia Occidentale, 600-400 A.c. : Scavi Sull'acropoli Di Monte Polizzo (TP), 2000-2003". *Sicilia Archeologica* 37, no. 102 (2004): 35–90.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No images of this deity have been discovered or identified among the material culture of the sanctuary.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

— Yes

Notes: The evidence shows that visitors were communicating (or attempting to communicate) with the gods through offerings and animal sacrifices.

Reference: Mühlenbock, Christian. *Fragments from a Mountain Society. Tradition, Innovation and Interaction at Archaic Monte Polizzo, Sicily.* GOTARC. Series B, Gothenburg Archaeological Theses. Göteborgs universitet, 2008.

Reference: Morris, Ian, Trinity Jackman, Brien Garnand, Emma Blake, Sebastiano Tusa, Pasquale Agozzino, Tara Hnatiuk, et al.. "Stanford University Excavations on the Acropolis of Monte Polizzo, Sicily, IV: Preliminary Report on the 2003 Season" 49 (2004). <https://doi.org/10.2307/4238823>.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

— Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

— Yes

Notes: Some of the thousands of deer antlers discovered in the sanctuary were modified in order to be attached to headdresses, which has lead scholars to speculate that perhaps they were worn during specific rituals honouring the titular deity of the sanctuary.

Reference: Öhlinger, Birgit. "Indigenous Cult Places of Local and Interregional Scale in Archaic Sicily: A Sociological Approach to Religion". Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2015.

Reference: Tusa, Sebastiano, and Ian Morris. "Scavi Sull'acropoli Di Monte Polizzo, 2000-2003". *Sicilia Archeologica* 37, no. 102 (2004): 35-90.

Reference: Tusa, Sebastiano. "Da Mokarta a Monte Polizzo: La Transizione Dall'età Del Bronzo Finale All'età Del Ferro". In *Eis Acra : Insediamenti D'altura in Sicilia Dalla Preistoria Al III Sec. A.c.*, 27-52. S. Sciascia, 2009.

Reference: Mühlenbock, C.. "Expanding the Circle of Trust: Tradition and Change in Iron Age Communities in Western Sicily". In *Tradition: Transmission of Culture in the Ancient World (= Danish Studies in Classical Archaeology, Acta Hyperborea 14)*, 239-68. Copenhagen, 2015.

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

— Yes

Notes: Sacrifices and/or burning of large animals in situ.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

— Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

—specify: Not possible to estimate.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

—specify: No sacred calendar from Monte Polizzo has survived, so it is not possible to answer this question.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

— Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

— Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

— Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

— Yes

Notes: Drinking vessels have been discovered around the sanctuary. It is plausible that ritual consumption of wine or other substances took place during religious celebrations.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

— Yes

Reference: Tusa, Sebastiano. "Da Mokarta a Monte Polizzo: La Transizione Dall'età Del Bronzo Finale All'età Del Ferro". In *Eis Acra : Insediamenti D'altura in Sicilia Dalla Preistoria Al III Sec. A.c.*, 27-52. S. Sciascia, 2009.

Reference: Öhlinger, Birgit. "Indigenous Cult Places of Local and Interregional Scale in Archaic Sicily: A Sociological Approach to Religion". Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2015.

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↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

— Yes [specify]: Red deer

Notes: More than 30,000 fragments of red deer bones, especially antlers and skulls, were discovered around building A1 and altar A2.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

— No

Notes: Fragments of human bones were indeed discovered in the sanctuary, but it is unclear whether they were part of rituals or graves that had been disturbed during any of the construction phases of the area.

Reference: Morris, Ian, and Sebastiano Tusa. "Religione E Mutamento Sociale in Sicilia Occidentale, 600-400 A.c. : Scavi Sull'acropoli Di Monte Polizzo (TP), 2000-2003". *Sicilia Archeologica* 37, no. 102 (2004): 35-90.

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

— No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

— No

Are material offerings present:

— Yes

Reference: Tusa, Sebastiano. "Da Mokarta a Monte Polizzo: La Transizione Dall'età Del Bronzo Finale All'età Del Ferro". In *Eis Acra : Insediamenti D'altura in Sicilia Dalla Preistoria Al III Sec. A.c.*, 27-52. S. Sciascia, 2009.

Reference: Öhlinger, Birgit. "Indigenous Cult Places of Local and Interregional Scale in Archaic Sicily: A Sociological Approach to Religion". Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2015.

Reference: Tusa, Sebastiano, and Ian Morris. "Scavi Sull'acropoli Di Monte Polizzo, 2000-2003". *Sicilia Archeologica* 37, no. 102 (2004): 35-90.

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

— Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

— Yes

Notes: The offerings include fine pottery, jewels, and worked bone, alongside spectacularly large deer antlers.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

— Yes

Notes: Alongside fine objects, the offerings include common pottery and objects for everyday

use (e.g. brooches)

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Notes: Many of the offerings were deposited in sacred pits around the main buildings of the sacred area.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not impossible that presence was mandatory for the whole community for specific occasions or festivities, but this hypothesis cannot be confirmed.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The main religious buildings, especially A1/A2/A5 were repaired and heavily modified at least twice during the 6th century BCE.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Many of the deer bones discovered in the area show traces of combustion.

Reference: Tusa, Sebastiano. "Da Mokarta a Monte Polizzo: La Transizione Dall'età Del Bronzo Finale All'età Del Ferro". In *Eis Acra : Insediamenti D'altura in Sicilia Dalla Preistoria Al III Sec. A.c., 27-52*. S. Sciascia, 2009.

Reference: Tusa, Sebastiano, and Ian Morris. "Scavi Sull'acropoli Di Monte Polizzo, 2000-2003". *Sicilia Archeologica* 37, no. 102 (2004): 35-90.

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: While there are traces of drinking activities and many of the animal bones show traces of combustion, there are no long bones typically associated with the consumption of meat. It is possible that the animals were butchered and cooked here and eaten somewhere else.

Reference: Tusa, Sebastiano. "Da Mokarta a Monte Polizzo: La Transizione Dall'età Del Bronzo Finale All'età Del Ferro". In *Eis Acra : Insediamenti D'altura in Sicilia Dalla Preistoria Al III Sec. A.c., 27-52*. S. Sciascia, 2009.

Reference: Tusa, Sebastiano, and Ian Morris. "Scavi Sull'acropoli Di Monte Polizzo, 2000-2003". *Sicilia Archeologica* 37, no. 102 (2004): 35-90.

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No religious calendar has survived so we cannot know for sure. However, given the ideological importance of this sanctuary for the local community, it is plausible that perhaps some festivals were celebrated in this place.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: As this sanctuary seems to have been strongly associated with the indigenous Elymian community, it is possible that there may have been specific ethnic requirements to join the local clergy, and that entrance to the sanctuary was restricted to community members.

Reference: Mühlenbock, Christian. *Fragments from a Mountain Society. Tradition, Innovation and Interaction at Archaic Monte Polizzo, Sicily.*. GOTARC. Series B, Gothenburg Archaeological Theses. Göteborgs universitet, 2008.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is plausible that the sanctuary was managed through a formal bureaucratic hierarchical system, but the archaeological data has not provided clues that could help verify this hypothesis.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Reference: Kolb, M.J., and W.M. Balco. "Indigenous Urbanism in Iron Age Western Sicily". In *Making Cities. Economies of Production and Urbanization in Mediterranean Europe, 1000-500 BC*, 281-98. Cambridge: McDonald Institute for Archaeological Research, 2021.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Notes: The city of Monte Polizzo controlled a large area of fertile land and its resources, as well as access to them. The agricultural products were supplemented by local production of wool, textiles, and especially pottery that were then exchanged with neighbours and traveling traders.

Reference: Mühlenbock, Christian. *Fragments from a Mountain Society. Tradition, Innovation and Interaction at Archaic Monte Polizzo, Sicily.*. GOTARC. Series B, Gothenburg Archaeological Theses. Göteborgs universitet, 2008.

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The remains of a building on the Acropolis have been tentatively identified as those of a granary. If this hypothesis were to be confirmed, it might mean that part of the generated surplus was collected by a central administration, stored, and perhaps distributed to the population on the Acropolis.

Reference: Mühlenbock, Christian. *Fragments from a Mountain Society. Tradition, Innovation and Interaction at Archaic Monte Polizzo, Sicily.*. GOTARC. Series B, Gothenburg Archaeological Theses. Göteborgs universitet, 2008.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No inscriptions or other written documents have been found in the sanctuary, but that does not mean that they were never there.

Reference: Mühlenbock, Christian. *Fragments from a Mountain Society. Tradition, Innovation and Interaction at Archaic Monte Polizzo, Sicily.*. GOTARC. Series B, Gothenburg Archaeological Theses. Göteborgs universitet, 2008.

Sciascia, 2009.

Reference: Yes, Morris, Ian, and Sebastiano Tusa. "Religione E Mutamento Sociale in Sicilia Occidentale, 600-400 A.c. : Scavi Sull'acropoli Di Monte Polizzo (TP), 2000-2003". *Sicilia Archeologica* 37, no. 102 (2004): 35-90.

Reference: Worship, Spatafora, Francesca. "Culti E Ceramiche Greche Nei Santuari Dei Centri Indigeni Della Sicilia Occidentale". In *Ceramica Attica Da Santuari Della Grecia, Della Ionia E Dell'italia, Atti Convegno Internazionale (perugia 14-17 Marzo 2007)*, 739-57. Bari, 2009. . . .